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Cross-Sectioning the Literacy Status of the Schools Division of Calbayog City

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ABSTRACT

This study cross-sectionally assessed the literacy status among schools in the Schools Division of Calbayog City. It employed a descriptive cross-sectional research design utilizing the EGRA, CRLA and Phil-IRI reading tools fielded out, developed and adopted as principal research instruments in this study. Results revealed that most Grade level learners yielded a significant decrease in the number of learners that are in full refresher and frustration level from pre-assessment result to mid-assessment results. There was a significant decrease in the number of learners identified with frustration level from pre-assessment result to mid-assessment result. Grades 7-12 did not show significant differences between their pre- and mid-assessment results for PHIL-IRI Filipino and English. Therefore, it is recommended that intensification of these tools and orientation to teachers relative to the conduct of the assessment processes may be instituted in the entire division.

INTRODUCTION

Because it has such a significant impact on how an individual can function within a society, literacy can be viewed as empowering. Literacy is traditionally defined as the capacity to read and write (Purcia & Merida, 2021). Currently, it refers to a person's competence in a particular field or discipline as well as their knowledge. A person's capacity for reading, writing, speaking, listening, conceptualization, and innovation opens up many opportunities. "Literacy encompasses the knowledge and skills students need to access, understand, analyze, and evaluate information, make meaning, express thoughts and emotions, present ideas and opinions, interact with others, and participate in activities at school and in their lives beyond school," according to the Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority (n.d.), educators have been interested in literacy education problems, issues, and trends for a very long time. in 2016, Ewing, para. 3).

Through surveys conducted by various experts in the field, the International Literacy Association (ILA) publishes a report on pressing issues pertaining to literacy education each year. According to Selangan (2015), these kinds of surveys are meant to "reveal wide gaps between what educators across the globe consider important topics in literacy education and those garnering the most attention." 1). Issues in literacy education are categorized as "hot" (those that receive a lot of attention) and "not hot" (those that are not popular and don't need a lot of attention) in accordance with the goal of ILA. In order to provide teachers, professors, researchers, administrators, and policymakers with information on issues that require immediate discussions and solutions, ILA has a tradition of presenting "hot" and "not hot" issues.

According to Cassidy & Ortlieb (2011), educators' interest in literacy education began in the 1990s when they observed significant gaps in the field's understanding of its development. However, many important issues were left unresolved because there were not enough studies and data to spread literacy education (Purcia, Albuladura & Velarde, 2021). As a result, literacy experts came up with the idea of compiling a list of timely and pertinent issues related to the field in order to assist their fellow advocates in putting their academic endeavors into context. "This body of work would allow us, as literacy professionals, to learn from the past and in turn, refine our practices to suit the ever-changing needs of the educational community," as stated by Cassidy & Ortlieb (2011).

According to a report published in 2000 by the Department of Education (DepEd), the literacy rate among Filipinos is 96.6 percent. In addition, the United Nations Development Report (2009) asserts that the Philippines has a high literacy rate of 93.4% (Imam, 2016), and the literacy rate of children was 98.2% in 2015 (Balinas, Rodriguez, Santillan, & Villena, 2017). Since a number of studies have demonstrated the alarming decline in reading proficiency among Filipino students over the past few years (Bacal, 2005; Imam, 2016; Luz, 2007; Orenca, 2006; & Selangan, 2015).

Contrarily, according to Cristobal (2015), 1.2 million Filipinos between the ages of five and fifteen are out of school and have limited literacy skills. Balinas, Rodriguez, Santillan, and Villena (2017) also show that remote Mindanao kindergarteners have consistently low reading scores. Luz's (2007) claim that the Philippines is "a nation of non-readers" may become one of the country's major challenges in the future if these numbers continue to rise. It is impossible to deny that the nation has encountered

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a number of difficulties, particularly with regard to the dissemination of its literacy education and its enhancement. Given that Imam (2016) stated that “without literacy, all other learning is impossible,” such issues cannot be ignored (para. 1). Nevertheless, he excludes poverty as the primary reason why many Filipinos struggle with literacy. Due to a lack of resources that will enable them to attend school and receive a decent education, many students cannot complete their education para. 4). Additionally, Graham & Perin (2007) emphasized that literacy is declining in the Philippines and that the three main causes are as follows: (1) corruption; (2) unqualified teachers and staff; and (3) the media that is hostile to intellectual thought.

Despite the fact that a number of studies have identified some of the issues associated with literacy education in the Philippines, it is evident that these identified issues are limited and may not fully clarify literacy issues that require immediate or significant attention. As a result, the researcher sought to provide a “clearer image” of literacy status in the Schools Division of Calbayog as a representative sample of the vast literacy population in the region and the nation in general.

Research Questions

This study cross-sectionally assessed Literacy status in the Schools Division of Calbayog for the SY 2022-2023.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions

1. What is the status of Literacy in the Schools Division of Calbayog City as assessed by teachers using EGRA, CRLA and Phil-IRI tools in terms of
 - 1.1 pre-assessment; and
 - 1.2 mid-assessment?
2. Is there a significant difference between the pre-assessment and mid-assessment results using the CRLA and Phil-IRI tools as assessed by teachers?
3. What problems do the teachers encounter in the process of assessment?
4. Based on the study’s findings, what program may be

proposed to improve the assessment process?

METHOD

This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional research design which assessed the literacy status in the Schools Division of Calbayog City for the SY 2022-2023. The EGRA, CRLA and Phil-IRI tools fielded out and developed were utilized and adopted as principal research instruments in this study. A checklist for the problems encountered by the teachers in the assessment was also administered. Data were gathered based on Regional Memorandum No. 965, s. 2022 on the scheme of specific time span when pre- and mid- assessments were conducted.

Further, data gathered were collated, tallied and analyzed based on identified research problems using SPSS version 28. A simple frequency count was used for both the pre-assessment and mid-assessment results. For the problems encountered, for the significant difference of the results for both pre and mid-assessments, paired sample t-test was used for both CRLA and Phil-IRI. Only the EGRA results were not subjected to inferential analysis due to the nature of the assessment tool which is developmental in context and that there is no available data yet for comparison since the post-assessment will still be undertaken.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tables below show the data analysis on both pre and mid-assessment results. (Please see Excel data for the frequency count of pre and mid-assessment results).

On the Significant Difference between the Pre and Mid-Assessment Results for both CRLA and Phil-IRI

The tables below present the inferential analysis on the significant difference between the pre and mid-assessment results of both the CRLA and Phil-IRI.

On the Significant Difference between the Pre and Mid-Assessment Results for both CRLA and Phil-IRI

The tables below present the inferential analysis on the significant difference between the pre and mid-assessment results of both the CRLA and Phil-IRI.

Table 1: CRLA Mother Tongue Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Grade 1 Pre-Assessment CRLA Mother Tongue	198.75	12	142.052	41.007
	108.92	12	64.814	18.710
Grade 1 Mid-Assessment CRLA Mother Tongue				
Pair 2 Grade 2 Pre-Assessment CRLA Mother Tongue	147.42	12	110.419	31.875
	81.42	12	52.528	151.163
Grade 2 Mid-Assessment CRLA Mother Tongue				
Pair 3 Grade 3 Pre-Assessment CRLA Mother Tongue	114.42	12	71.327	20.590
	77.92	12	44.449	12.831
Grade 3 Mid-Assessment CRLA Mother Tongue				

Table 2: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Grade 1 Pre-Assessment	89.833	111.175	32.094	19.196	160.471	2.799	11	0.017
CRLA Mother Tongue								
Grade 1 Mid-Assessment								
CRLA Mother Tongue	66	73.108	21.104	19.55	112.45	3.127	11	0.01
Pair 2 Grade 2 Pre-Assessment								
CRLA Mother Tongue								
Grade 2 Mid-Assessment	36.5	45.065	13.009	7.867	65.133	2.806	11	0.017
CRLA Mother Tongue								
Grade 3 Mid-Assessment								
CRLA Mother Tongue								

Grades 1,2,3 have significant differences between their pre- and mid assessment results for CRLA Mother Tongue. There was significant decrease in the number of learners

that are in full refresher from pre-assessment result to mid-assessment result. Grade 2 pre- and mid assessment results have a significant difference for CRLA Filipino.

Table 3: CRLA FILIPINO Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Grade 2 Pre-Assessment	142.25	12	107.833	31.129
CRLA Filipino				
Grade 2 Mid-Assessment	74.25	12	41.379	11.945
CRLA Filipino				
Pair 2 Grade 3 Pre-Assessment	114.83	12	80.753	23.311
CRLA Filipino				
Grade 3 Mid-Assessment	99.08	12	109.089	31.491
CRLA Filipino				

Table 4: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Grade 2 Pre-Assessment	68	82.461	23.804	15.607	120.393	2.857	11	0.016
CRLA Filipino								
Grade 2 Mid-Assessment								
CRLA Filipino	15.75	73.33	21.169	-30.842	62.342	0.744	11	0.472
Pair 2 Grade 3 Pre-Assessment								
CRLA Filipino								
Grade 3 Mid-Assessment								
CRLA Filipino								

The number of learners who were in the full refresher decreased after the mid-assessment result. No significant

difference was found in pre- and mid assessment results of Grade 3 for CRLA Filipino.

Table 5: CRLA ENGLISH Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Grade 3 Pre-Assessment	98.67	12	52.574	15.177
CRLA English				
Grade 3 Mid-Assessment	61.25	12	32.1	9.266
CRLA English				

Table 6: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Grade 3 Pre-Assessment								
CRLA English	37.417	44.005	12.703	9.457	65.376	2.945	11	0.013
Grade 3 Mid-Assessment								
CRLA English								

Grade 3 pre- and mid assessment results have a significant difference for CRLA English. The number of learners who were in the full refresher decreased after the mid-assessment result in CRLA English.

Table 7: GRADE 4-6 PHIL-IRI FILIPINO Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Grade 4 Pre-Assessment	107.58	12	47.368	13.674
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Grade 4 Mid-Assessment	71.58	12	30.42	8.781
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Pair 2 Grade 5 Pre-Assessment	98	12	58.574	16.909
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Grade 5 Mid-Assessment	54.5	12	36.567	10.556
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Pair 3 Grade 6 Pre-Assessment	73.17	12	49.023	14.152
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Grade 6 Mid-Assessment	39.5	12	29.583	8.54
Phil-IRI Filipino				

Table 8: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Grade 4 Pre-Assessment	36	27.472	7.931	18.545	53.455	4.539	11	0.001
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Grade 4 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Pair 2 Grade 5 Pre-Assessment								
Phil-IRI Filipino	43.5	38.855	11.217	18.813	68.187	3.878	11	0.003
Grade 5 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI Filipino								

Pair 3 Grade 6 Pre-Assessment	33.667	38.306	11.058	9.328	58.005	3.045	11	0.011
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Grade 6 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI Filipino								

Grades 4, 5, and 6 showed significant differences between their pre- and mid assessment results for PHIL-IRI Filipino. There was significant decrease in the number of learners identified in frustration level from pre-

assessment result to mid-assessment result.

Grades 7, 8, 9, and 10 did not show significant differences between their pre- and mid assessment results for PHIL-IRI Filipino.

Table 9: GRADE 7-10 PHIL-IRI FILIPINO, Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Grade 7 Pre-Assessment	80.583	12	67.4745	19.4782
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Grade 7 Mid-Assessment	54.917	12	35.2664	10.1805
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Pair 2 Grade 8 Pre-Assessment	54.917	12	40.0374	11.5578
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Grade 8 Mid-Assessment	39.083	12	29.6233	8.5515
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Pair 3 Grade 9 Pre-Assessment	62.833	12	62.7098	18.1028
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Grade 9 Mid-Assessment	42.667	12	53.5729	15.4652
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Pair 4 Grade 10 Pre-Assessment	49.833	12	53.6891	15.4987
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Grade 10 Mid-Assessment	29.917	12	27.1141	7.8272
Phil-IRI Filipino				

Table 10: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Grade 7 Pre-Assessment	25.6667	51.0104	14.7254	-6.7438	58.0771	1.743	11	0.109
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Grade 7 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Pair 2 Grade 8 Pre-Assessment	15.8333	39.863	11.5075	-9.4944	41.1611	1.376	11	0.196
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Grade 8 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Pair 3 Grade 9 Pre-Assessment	20.1667	69.5764	20.085	-24.0401	64.3734	1.004	11	0.337
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Grade 9 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Pair 4 Grade 10 Pre-Assessment	19.9167	37.597	10.8533	-3.9714	43.8047	1.835	11	0.094
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Grade 10 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI Filipino								

Grades 11 and 12 also did not show significant differences between their pre- and mid assessment results for PHIL-IRI Filipino
Grades 4, 5, and 6 showed significant differences between

their pre- and mid assessment results for PHIL-IRI English. There was significant decrease in the number of learners identified in frustration level from pre-assessment result to mid-assessment result.

Table 11: GRADE 11-12 PHIL-IRI FILIPINO, Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Grade 11 Pre-Assessment	24.750	12	25.2807	7.2979
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Grade 11 Mid-Assessment	13.917	12	14.1322	4.0796
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Pair 2 Grade 12 Pre-Assessment	39.500	12	45.8287	13.2296
Phil-IRI Filipino				
Grade 12 Mid-Assessment	19.083	12	19.1000	5.5137
Phil-IRI Filipino				

Table 12: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Grade 11 Pre-Assessment	10.8333	18.5660	5.3595	-.9630	22.6296	2.021	11	.068
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Grade 11 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Pair 2 Grade 12 Pre-Assessment	20.4167	32.6119	9.4143	-.3040	41.1373	2.169	11	.053
Phil-IRI Filipino								
Grade 12 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI Filipino								

Table 13: GRADE 4-6 PHIL-IRI ENGLISH, Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Grade 4 Pre-Assessment	116.67	12	50.694	14.634
Phil-IRI English				
Grade 4 Mid-Assessment	84.75	12	39.724	11.467
Phil-IRI English				
Pair 2 Grade 5 Pre-Assessment	120.25	12	53.997	15.588
Phil-IRI English				
Grade 5 Mid-Assessment	75.25	12	42.437	12.251
Phil-IRI English				
Pair 3 Grade 6 Pre-Assessment	97.417	12	66.1314	19.0905
Phil-IRI English				
Grade 6 Mid-Assessment	59	12	32.7136	9.4436
Phil-IRI English				

Table 14: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Grade 4 Pre-Assessment	31.917	29.172	8.421	13.382	50.452	3.79	11	0.003
Phil-IRI English								
Grade 4 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI English								
Pair 2 Grade 5 Pre-Assessment	45	28.54	8.239	26.866	63.134	5.462	11	0
Phil-IRI English								
Grade 5 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI English								
Pair 3 Grade 6 Pre-Assessment	38.4167	42.348	12.2248	11.51	65.3233	3.143	11	0.009
Phil-IRI English								
Grade 6 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI English								

Grades 7, 8, and 10 showed significant differences between their pre- and mid assessment results for PHIL-IRI English. There was significant decrease in the number of learners identified in frustration level from pre-

assessment result to mid-assessment result in these grade levels. However, no significant difference was found for the pre- and mid assessment results of Grade 10 students in Phil-IRI English.

Table 15: GRADE 7-10 PHIL-IRI ENGLISH, Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Grade 7 Pre-Assessment	107.583	12	74.4842	21.5017
Phil-IRI English				
Grade 7 Mid-Assessment	71.75	12	45.8121	13.2248
Phil-IRI English				
Pair 2 Grade 8 Pre-Assessment	87.083	12	59.7532	17.2493
Phil-IRI English				
Grade 8 Mid-Assessment	52.833	12	32.9596	9.5146
Phil-IRI English				
Pair 3 Grade 9 Pre-Assessment	102.667	12	74.6267	21.5429
Phil-IRI English				
Grade 9 Mid-Assessment	65.917	12	55.1435	15.9186
Phil-IRI English				
Pair 4 Grade 10 Pre-Assessment	87.833	12	68.8144	19.865
Phil-IRI English				
Grade 10 Mid-Assessment	47.25	12	36.4246	10.5149
Phil-IRI English				

Table 16: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Grade 7 Pre-Assessment	35.8333	54.4039	15.7051	1.2667	70.3999	2.282	11	0.043
Phil-IRI English								

Phil-IRI English								
Grade 7 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI English								
Pair 2 Grade 8 Pre-Assessment	34.25	45.9469	13.2637	5.0568	63.4432	2.582	11	0.025
Phil-IRI English								
Grade 8 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI English								
Pair 3 Grade 9 Pre-Assessment	36.75	79.582	22.9733	-13.814	87.314	1.6	11	0.138
Phil-IRI English								
Grade 9 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI English								
Pair 4 Grade 10 Pre-Assessment	40.5833	58.1041	16.7732	3.6658	77.5009	2.42	11	0.034
Phil-IRI English								
Grade 10 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI English								

Table 17: GRADE 11-12 PHIL-IRI ENGLISH, Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 Grade 11 Pre-Assessment	45.333	12	44.7931	12.9307
Phil-IRI English				
Grade 11 Mid-Assessment	29.75	12	29.6713	8.5654
Phil-IRI English				
Pair 2 Grade 12 Pre-Assessment	24.5	12	31.9218	9.215
Phil-IRI English				
Grade 12 Mid-Assessment	19.167	12	24.0297	6.9368
Phil-IRI English				

Table 18: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Grade 11 Pre-Assessment	15.5833	32.3151	9.3286	-4.9487	36.1154	1.67	11	0.123
Phil-IRI English								
Grade 11 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI English								
Pair 2 Grade 12 Pre-Assessment	5.3333	29.626	8.5523	-13.4901	24.1568	0.624	11	0.546
Phil-IRI English								
Grade 12 Mid-Assessment								
Phil-IRI English								

Grades 11 and 12 also did not show significant differences between their pre- and mid assessment results for PHIL-IRI English.

On the Problems Encountered by the Teachers

during Assessment

Various problems relative to the assessment process confronted the teachers especially on the constraint on time and rigors. The table below presents the frequency and percentage distribution of these problems.

Table 19: Problems Encountered by Teachers on the Assessment Process

Problems Encountered	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
1. The request to submit for immediate results wherein the process requires time	1,965	85.6%	1
2. Attendance of learners during the assessment	1,893	82.5%	2
3. Preparedness of the learners for the tools used in the assessment	1,523	66.4%	4
4. Learning/Reading Retention of learners	1,024	44.6%	6
5. Lack of parents' support especially on the follow-ups of learning/reading activities	1,846	80.4%	3
6. Time constraint on the assessment process	978	42.6%	7
7. Readiness and preparedness of teachers on the conduct of the assessments	1245	54.6%	5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, for CRLA Grades 1,2,3 results showed significant decrease in the number of learners that are in full refresher from pre-assessment result to mid-assessment result . No significant difference was found in pre-and mid assessment results of Grade 3 for CRLA Filipino. The number of learners who were in the full refresher decreased after the mid-assessment result in CRLA English for Grade 3. There was significant decrease in the number of learners identified in frustration level from pre-assessment result to mid-assessment result. Grades 7, 8, 9, and 10 did not show significant differences between their pre- and mid assessment results for PHIL-IRI Filipino. Grades 11 and 12 also did not show significant differences between their pre- and mid assessment results for PHIL-IRI Filipino. There was significant decrease in the number of learners identified in frustration level from pre-assessment result to mid-assessment result for Grades 4, 5, and 6. For Grades 7, 8, and 10, there was significant decrease in the number of learners identified in frustration level from pre-assessment result to mid-assessment result in these grade levels. However, no significant difference was found for the pre- and mid assessment results of Grade 10 students in Phil-IRI English. Grades 11 and 12 also did not show significant differences between their pre- and mid assessment results for PHIL-IRI English. Consequently, intensifying the utilization of reading assessment tools and strengthened orientation to teachers relative to the conduct of the assessment processes may be instituted in the entire division.

REFERENCES

ACT. (2006). Reading between the lines: What the ACT reveals about college readiness in reading. Iowa City, IA: Author.

Bacal, E. (2005). Improving the Oral Reading Ability of Pupils. Manila.

Balinas, E., Santillan, J., Rodriguez, J., & Valencia, Y. (2017). Remedial Reading Program of AUF-CED: Best Practices and Impact. *4th Asia Pacific Education*

Conference (pp. 83-93). Purwokerto: Atlantis Press.

Cassidy, J., Ortlieb, E., & Shettel, J. (2010/2011). What's hot, what's not for 2011. *Reading Today*, 28.

Department of Education. (2000). Datasets. Retrieved from Department of Education: <http://www.deped.gov.ph/resources/facts-and-figures/datasheets/>

Graham, S., & Perin, D. (2007). Writing next: Effective strategies to improve writing of adolescents in middle and high schools-A report to Carnegie Corporation of New York. Washington, DC: Alliance for Excellent Education.

Imam, O. (2016). Effects of Reading Skills on Students' Performance in Science and Mathematics in Public and Private Secondary Schools. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 10(2), 177-186.

Luz, J. M. (2007). A nation of nonreaders. Quezon: Philippine Center for Investigative Journalism.

Miguel, F. (1996). Metacognitive learning strategies in reading: Their effects on writing competence. Doctoral dissertation, University of the Philippines-Diliman.

National Governors Association Center for Best Practices. (2005). Reading to achieve: A governor's guide to adolescent literacy. Washington, DC: Author.

Orencia, M. A. (2006). Enhancing Pupils Reading Comprehension and Attitudes through a Whole Language-Inspired Literature-Based Reading Program. *CELEA Journal*, 29(3), 3-18.

Purcia, E. L., & Merida, L. H. (2021). Faculty and Students' Evaluation of K to 12 English Curriculum in a Philippine Countryside University. *English philology*, 21, 1045-1059.

Purcia, E., Albuladura, A., & Velarde, A. (2021). Quality Management System (QMS) and Personnel Commitment: The Case of Calbayog City National High School.

Selangan. (2015). The Reading Profile of Children in the Philippines. Retrieved from George Lucas Educational Foundation. <http://www.edutopia.org/discussion/reading-profile-children-philippines>